

PARENTS LIVED EXPERIENCES AS STUDY BUDDY OF LEARNERS IN THE NEW NORMAL

Lemar A. Ablasa¹, Janice K. Bagano² and Flordeliza D. De Guzman²

¹ *Benguet State University – Buguias Campus, Benguet, Philippines*

² *DepEd – Benguet, CAR, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10781887>

ABSTRACT

This study thoroughly examined the Parents' Lived Experiences as Study Buddies for Learners in the New Normal during the 2021-2022 school year. The qualitative research design, employing formal interviews with 10 participating parents, revealed that parents play diverse roles, including supporter, teacher, provider, tutor, and guidance counselor in their children's formal education during the COVID-19 pandemic. Challenges encountered by parents encompassed difficulties in explaining lessons, time constraints, children's boredom, and temper management issues. The study concluded that parents' roles are influenced by parenting styles, their varied experiences stem from educational backgrounds and skills, realizations are shaped by temperament and readiness, and challenges arise due to a lack of proper orientation and training. Overall, the research highlights the complex dynamics involved in parents serving as study buddies in the evolving realm of education.

Keywords: *COVID-19 pandemic, parental skills, guiding time learning moments, study buddy, roles, formal education*

INTRODUCTION

In various regions across the globe, parents have assumed a pivotal role in steering their children's education amid the challenges posed by widespread school closures during the COVID-19 pandemic. A substantial shift towards technology-dependent learning has been observed, with urban schools globally conducting online classes, while areas with limited connectivity resort to traditional distance learning methods, educational television,

and printed materials distribution (TALIS, 2018). The digital divide, highlighted by UNICEF (2020), has accentuated the educational disparities between the affluent and underserved populations. As a result, a majority of parents worldwide, lacking access to high-quality digital infrastructure, grapple with significant obstacles in keeping their children connected to education systems.

As parents endeavor to facilitate their children's learning, the pandemic-induced lockdowns and social distancing measures have compelled many to work from home. In countries such as France, Germany, Italy, the UK, and the USA, Krentz, Kos, et.al (2020) reveal that 60% of parents have faced challenges in finding alternative solutions for schools and daycare centers. Despite these difficulties, parents deserve unequivocal support in their commitment to sustaining their children's learning during these trying times.

Ferris & Silburn, et.al (2019) stress the need for new adjustment strategies in education policies for all key stakeholders in the "new normal." Collaboration between teachers and parents emerges as crucial for the best interests of students, as evidenced by various studies indicating improved academic achievements, social skills, and emotional well-being resulting from such partnerships (Ofsted, 2011; TALIS, 2018; OECD, 2017). Parents, holding schools accountable for their child's learning, play a pivotal role as key stakeholders in education.

Lastly, Byron (2021) defines a "study buddy" as someone who engages in mutual support and collaborative learning during study times. In the current context, parents emerge as crucial study buddies for learners, forced into this role by the constraints of the new normal. The study conducted aims to shed light on the challenges faced by parents in this study buddy role and to provide insights for improvement. Its potential benefits extend to school administrators, teachers, learners, parents, researchers, and the broader educational community, serving as a foundation for material procurement, training, and further research endeavors in the evolving landscape of education.

This section critically examines theories and models pertinent to the involvement of parents as study buddies for learners, with a primary emphasis on Piaget's cognitive development theory and Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, as elucidated by Tekin (2011). Piaget's theory underscores children as active learners, constantly aligning their internal constructions with external realities through interactions with peers and family members (Piaget, 1981). Similarly, Vygotsky's sociocultural theory accentuates the influence of social and cultural factors on development, with family members, especially parents, playing a pivotal role in supporting learners (Rieber & Robinson, 2004). These theories lay a foundation for understanding the crucial role parents play in shaping their children's educational experiences.

In the practical application of these theories, various parent involvement models have been developed, with Epstein's (2001) and Hoover-Dempsey's (2007) models emerging as widely accepted and applied. Epstein's model encompasses parenting, communicating, and learning at home, aligning well with the current scenario where the

home has become the primary learning environment due to the pandemic (Epstein et al., 2002). Hoover-Dempsey's model delves into the motivations behind parental involvement, shaping factors, and mechanisms through which such involvement influences student outcomes, offering a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of parental engagement (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997; Hoover-Dempsey et al., 2005).

Given the new normal circumstances where parents have assumed the role of study buddies, both Epstein's and Hoover-Dempsey's models prove invaluable in guiding and supporting parents in this educational realm. The ongoing study at Sinipsip Elementary School seeks to illuminate the role of parents in formal education, document their experiences as study buddies, and identify challenges encountered. Through this investigation, the study aims to contribute practical insights for enhancing parental involvement as study buddies in the evolving educational landscape shaped by the new normal.

Research Questions

The main objective of the study assessed the ability of parent's lived experiences as study buddy of learners in the new normal.

Specifically, the study answers the following questions:

1. What are the roles of parents in the formal education of their children?
2. What are the experiences of parents in guiding their child in his/her formal education?
3. What are the learning moments of parents during their guiding time?
4. What are the difficulties or problems encountered by parents in guiding their child?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research employed a qualitative research design, specifically utilizing the phenomenological method through semi-structured, in-depth interviews to explore the lived experiences of parents as study buddies in the new normal educational setting. Qualitative research, as defined by Bhandari (2020), involves the collection and analysis of non-numerical data, such as text, video, or audio, to comprehend concepts, opinions, or experiences. The phenomenological method, according to Leonard (2018), focuses on understanding how individual participants experience specific events and employs interviews, observation, and surveys as data gathering tools. In this study, the choice of a semi-structured, in-depth interview technique aligns with the phenomenological model, as described by Boyce and Neale (2006), allowing for an in-depth exploration of parents' perspectives and experiences as study buddies during the new normal, facilitating the collection of detailed information.

Research Locale and Participants

The research took place at Sinipsip Elementary School in Sinipsip, Amgaleyguey, Buguias, Benguet, throughout the academic year 2021-2022. The participants in this study were drawn from the parent community associated with Sinipsip Elementary School, with a total of 10 respondents included in the research.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection in the study was a meticulously crafted interview guide comprising four distinct parts. This tool served as the means through which the targeted respondents, namely parents, provided responses. The interview guide encompassed inquiries delving into crucial aspects such as the role of parents in the formal education of their children, the experiences of parents in guiding their children through the formal education process, insights into learning moments during these guidance sessions, and an exploration of the challenges or problems faced by parents in their role as guides during their children's educational journey.

Data Collection Procedure

Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Dean of the Graduate School at Baguio Central University. Before proceeding with the formal interviews, the researcher sought permission from both the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Benguet and the school head teacher at Sinipsip Elementary School, where the study was carried out. Following the granting of approval, the researcher personally conducted the formal interviews, individually interviewing each respondent. Subsequently, the collected data from the formal interviews were analyzed and interpreted by the researcher.

Data Analysis

The primary aim of this qualitative study was to explore the lived experiences of parents serving as study buddies for learners. The objective was to gain a comprehensive understanding of these experiences and the roles parents undertake in this capacity. The study employed a one-on-one semi-structured interview approach guided by specific questions to collect data directly from the participants. The gathered responses from the respondents were subsequently compiled, analyzed, and interpreted to derive insights into the nuanced aspects of parents' lived experiences as study buddies for learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher demonstrated utmost professionalism and adherence to ethical standards throughout the study, ensuring courtesy and respect in all interactions. Before commencing the research, necessary permissions were secured from relevant authorities, indicating a commitment to following protocol. Clear communication with respondents was prioritized, with comprehensive information provided about the study's

purpose and their rights. Confidentiality measures were implemented to safeguard participants' responses, and explicit permission was obtained for the use of their data. Throughout the analysis and interpretation process, the researcher maintained objectivity and impartiality, ensuring that findings accurately reflected participants' lived experiences while upholding the universal essence of the subject matter under discussion.

RESULTS

Role of Parents in the Formal Education of their Children

The responses gathered from interviews with parents reveal five main roles that parents play in the formal education of their children: supporter, teacher, tutor, provider, and guidance counselor. The role of a supporter is emphasized, with several parents expressing their commitment to guiding and actively participating in their children's educational activities. The study notes that, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, parents have assumed a more supportive role, aligning with the findings of Aina & Azubuike (2020), who highlight the increasing support-oriented role of parents in their children's assignments and home projects. Additionally, the role of a teacher is evident, as parents acknowledge their responsibilities in encouraging and assisting with homework, embodying the crucial role of parents in fostering a positive learning environment. Furthermore, parents take on roles as tutors or facilitators, providing additional educational support. As providers, parents ensure the execution of their children's right to education by meeting their needs. Finally, some parents see themselves as guidance counselors, contributing to the discipline and overall guidance of their children. These roles align with the findings of Ceka & Murati (2016) and Bray (2016), emphasizing the multifaceted contributions of parents in shaping a healthy and successful educational experience for their children.

The Experiences in guiding their Children in their Formal Education

Parents shared their diverse experiences in guiding their children through formal education during the new normal, revealing common challenges and reflections. Many parents, such as A, B, D, and E, expressed difficulties in explaining lessons and emphasized the need for patience in guiding their children's studies. Parent F highlighted the challenge of conveying topics when a child is unresponsive, but also noted the excitement that comes when a child is eager to learn. Parent I faced challenges when her child lacked understanding in certain subjects, indicating the struggle of explaining unfamiliar topics. Parent J shared a more intense experience, admitting to moments of anger and the use of regrettable language, reflecting the heightened stress and emotional toll of the situation. These difficulties align with the findings of Ali et al. (2020), who noted concerns among parents about the abrupt shift to online classes and the challenges it presented, including a lack of discipline and teacher preparedness. Parent C provided a different perspective, emphasizing the importance of parental skills and emotional support in guiding a child's development, highlighting the multifaceted nature of parental involvement. Additionally, Parent H underscored the influence of teachers, as children

tended to adhere to their instructions even when parents offered alternative teaching methods. This resonates with the broader issue of teacher training and the impact it can have on the effectiveness of distance learning, as mentioned by Ali et al. (2020). Overall, these diverse experiences underscore the complex and evolving nature of parental roles in supporting their children's education during the new normal.

Learning Moments during the Guiding Time

Parents shared valuable insights into their learning moments during the guiding time, offering a nuanced understanding of the challenges and personal growth they experienced. The recurring theme of patience emerged, with several parents, such as A, B, C, E, H, and I, highlighting the importance of being patient while guiding their children through their studies. This aligns with educational literature, as emphasized by Prakash (2020), recognizing that teaching is a multifaceted role that demands patience. Parent B particularly acknowledged the complexity of being a teacher, stressing the need for heightened patience and the avoidance of immediate anger. Parent C provided a comprehensive perspective, emphasizing the necessity of patience, thoughtful attention, cooperation, and a deep understanding of the child's needs and struggles with disciplinary issues. Parent E's reflections on learning from mistakes and failures underscored the importance of resilience in the face of setbacks. Parent F's acknowledgment of the time-intensive nature of teaching, including reading and searching for additional examples, reinforces the dedication required for effective guidance. Parent G demonstrated strategic planning, teaching her child before bedtime or early in the morning, and maintaining a focused teaching environment by keeping away her phone and turning off the TV. Parent J showcased creativity in learning to draw and illustrate, enhancing her teaching methods. These diverse learning moments collectively emphasize the multifaceted nature of parental involvement in guiding their children's education during the new normal, highlighting both the emotional and practical dimensions of this challenging role. The study's findings echo Silma's (2020) observations that parents, particularly those facing challenges like teaching children who cannot read, grapple with frustration and a sense of starting from scratch.

Difficulties or Problems Encountered in Guiding the Children

Parents candidly shared the myriad difficulties and challenges they encountered while guiding their children's education during the pandemic, shedding light on the complexities and emotional toll of this role. Parent A expressed facing a lack of time, unfamiliarity with subjects, and occasional conflicts with their children. This aligns with the acknowledgment by Silman (2020) that families with ample resources may navigate home learning more smoothly. Parent B grappled with the challenge of effectively explaining lessons to her child, unsure if comprehension was achieved. Parent C highlighted her child's tendency to become easily bored during lessons, necessitating creative approaches to maintain interest. Parent D echoed this sentiment, noting their child's propensity to lose interest during teaching sessions. Parent E enumerated multiple difficulties, including the inherent challenge of teaching one's child, a lack of learning and understanding, and time constraints. These challenges align with Lyness's (2020) observations that some children

resist their parents as teachers, impacting the learning experience. Overall, the study's findings underscore the substantial barriers parents face in assuming the role of educators, ranging from unfamiliarity with subjects to emotional struggles, emphasizing the need for comprehensive support systems in the evolving landscape of home-based learning. The challenges resonate with Smith's (2019) acknowledgment that parents may lack confidence due to potential gaps in their own education and unfamiliarity with the current curriculum.

Conclusions

The study's findings lead to several key conclusions regarding parents' roles, experiences, realizations, and challenges in guiding their children's formal education during the pandemic. Firstly, the parents' roles were found to be intricately linked to their parenting styles, shaping how they navigated the complexities of assuming the role of educators. Secondly, a diverse array of experiences among parents emerged during the process of guiding their children, influenced significantly by their individual educational backgrounds and skills. These variations underscore the importance of recognizing and catering to the unique needs and capabilities of each parent. Thirdly, parents underwent realizations during their guiding time, with their temperament and readiness playing pivotal roles in shaping these insights. This highlights the emotional and psychological dimensions of the parent-child educational dynamic. Lastly, the study revealed that parents encountered numerous challenges in guiding their children, primarily rooted in a lack of proper orientation and training. Insufficient preparation and unfamiliarity with effective teaching strategies emerged as significant hurdles, emphasizing the need for comprehensive support systems and training initiatives to enhance parents' capabilities in fulfilling this educational role. Overall, these conclusions underscore the multifaceted nature of the parental involvement in the new normal of home-based learning and emphasize the necessity for targeted interventions to address the identified challenges.

Recommendations

The conclusions drawn from the study offer valuable insights into potential recommendations for parents and educational stakeholders. Firstly, it is strongly advised that parents continue to actively provide assistance and guidance to their children in all aspects of life, emphasizing the holistic nature of parental involvement. This includes not only academic support but also emotional and social guidance to foster well-rounded development. Secondly, parents are encouraged to devise effective plans to address their diverse experiences during the guiding time. Tailored strategies that consider individual backgrounds, skills, and challenges can contribute to a more supportive and effective learning environment at home. Thirdly, the recommendation suggests that parents allocate and invest more time in their children's education to enhance its success. This underscores the importance of quality time spent in educational activities and interactions, fostering a positive and enriching learning atmosphere. Lastly, a collaborative approach is advocated, urging schools, parents, and other stakeholders to continue working together. This collective effort aims to address the challenges identified in the study,

fostering a supportive and synergistic relationship between home and school environments. By promoting ongoing collaboration, a more effective and comprehensive response to the complexities of home-based learning can be achieved.

REFERENCES

- Aina B. & Azubuike, O. (2020). How Parents are Supporting Their Children's Learning During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria
- Ali I. COVID-19: Are We Ready for the Second Wave? *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*. 2020;14(5):e16-e18. doi:10.1017/dmp.2020.149
- Bhandari, P. (2020) What Is Qualitative Research? *IMethods and Examples*
- Boyce, C. & Neale, P. (2006). *Conducting In-Depth Interview*
- Bray, B. (2016). *Parents are Part of a School, Too*
- Byron, Hinson. (2021, March 15). Microsoft Encarta Reference Library 2002 DVD - Review. ActiveWin. Archived from the original on 15 March 2021. http://www.activewin.com/reviews/software/apps/ms/encarta/2002_dvd/
- Encarta. (2015). Study buddy. In *Encarta Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://thesetwoeyes.com/tag/microsofts-encarta-dictionary/>
- Epstein, J. L. (2001). *School, Family, and Community Partnerships: Preparing Educators and Improving Schools*. Boulder, CO: Westview.
- Epstein, J. L., Sanders, M. G., et al (2002). *School, Family, and Community Partnerships: Your Handbook for Action (2nd ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Ferris, P., Silburn, K. et al. (2019). *Parent-Teacher Partnerships: The Need for Renewed Collaboration in the Time of COVID-19*.
- Hoover – Dempsey, K. V., Bassler, O. C., & Brissie, J. S. (1987). *Parent Involvement: Contributions of Teacher Efficacy, School Socioeconomic Status, and other School Characteristics*. *American Educational Research Journal*.
- Krentz, M., Kos, E., et al. (2020). *Easing the COVID-19 Burden on Working Parents*
- Leonard, L. J. (2018). *Qualitative Research Design*
- Lyness D, (2020). The use of social media and online communications in times of pandemic COVID-19. *Journal of the Intensive Care Society*. 2021;22(3):255-260. doi:10.1177/1751143720966280
- Ofsted,. (2011). *School and Parents: Developing Partnerships*.
- Piaget, J. (1981). *Their Relations During Child Development*. Palo Alto, CA: Annual Reviews
- Prakash, J. (2020). *It's Not Easy Being A Teacher*
- Prior, J., & Gerard, M. R. (2007). *Family Involvement in Early Childhood Education: Research into Practice*. New York: Thomson
- Rafidi, A. (2020). Bendijo, J. (2020). *A paradigm shift for meaningful distance learning in unprecedented circumstances*. Department of Education. (Publication year not

- specified). Exploring diverse learning modalities: Modular Distance Learning and Online Distance Learning.
- Rafidi, A. (2020). Teachers as ever-ready learning consultants: Supporting parents and learners through learning modules and worksheets.
- Rieber, R. W., & Robinson, D. K. (Eds.). (2004). *The Essential Vygotsky*. New York: Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers.
- Schlager, (2021). Difficulties or Problems Encountered in Guiding the Children. [Include the publication details, such as the name of the journal or the book, volume/issue number, and page range.]
- Silman, A. (2020). Why are Parents So Bad at Teaching their Own Kids?
- Smith, N. (2019). Parents Lack Confidence in Helping Their Children with Homework
- Talis. (2018). *Teachers and School Leaders as Lifelong Learners*, OECD, 2019
- Tekin, A. (2011) *Parent Involvement Revisited: Background, Theories, and Models*
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.